
STRATEGIC AGILITY AND THE PERFORMANCE OF FAST-MOVING CONSUMER GOODS (FMCG) FIRMS IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Strategic agility research is growing among managers, firms and academic researchers. It is a burning area in management and economic research. Regrettably, strategic agility and the performance for fast-moving consumer goods firms are yet to gain the expected relevance in emerging market such as Nigeria. The study was conducted to ascertain the influence of strategic agility on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) firms in South West, Nigeria. Clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core capabilities, were the dimensions of strategic agility in this study. Survey research design was adopted and structured self-administered questionnaire were administered to a sample size of 332 management staff of the selected fast-moving consumer goods firms. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Clarity of vision showed a statistically significant influence on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms with ($B = 0.884$, $p < 0.000$, R -value of 0.639), strategic leadership showed a statistically significant influence of ($B = 0.857$, $p < 0.000$, R -value of 0.672), core competence showed a statistically significant influence of ($B = 0.962$, $p > 0.000$, R -value of 0.681). Findings revealed that there is a significant influence of strategic agility variable used in this study on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in South West, Nigeria. It was concluded that strategic agility dimensions are relational dimensions that can influence the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms. It was recommended that, firms in the FMCG should be strategically sensitive to its environment by engaging in continuous environmental scanning to identify emerging consumer preferences and industry shifts.

Keyword: Strategic Agility, Performance, Clarity of vision, Strategic Leadership, Core Capabilities and FMCG

1. Introduction

The Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) firms in Nigeria operates in a highly dynamic and competitive environment, influenced by economic fluctuations, changing consumer preferences, regulatory policies, and technological advancements. To sustain growth and profitability, FMCG firms must continuously adapt to market disruptions and evolving business conditions. Strategic agility, which encompasses an organisation's ability to swiftly sense market changes, align leadership decisions, and reallocate resources efficiently, plays a crucial role in enhancing firm performance. By leveraging strategic agility, FMCG firms in Nigeria can improve operational efficiency, foster innovation, and maintain a competitive edge in an increasingly volatile marketplace.

In Nigeria's FMCG sector, firms with agile strategies such as clarity of vision, strategic leadership, core capabilities, strategic sensitivity and resource fluidity can quickly adapt to changing market conditions, align their operations with consumer demands, and innovate to deliver value-added products (Deshati, 2023). Strategic agility enables organisations to mitigate risks, improve operational efficiency, and achieve competitive advantage in a rapidly evolving market. According to Olaleye *et al.* (2018), most Nigerian fast-moving consumer goods firms have had inconsistent success due to sluggish agile responses to difficulties such as political intervention, lack of transparency, regulatory uncertainty and policy instability and insufficient infrastructural facilities. Furthermore, Nurjaman *et al.* (2021) noted that enterprises in various industries' lack strategic agility in responding to these difficulties has resulted to inconsistent firm success in Nigeria.

According to Mutunga *et al.* (2024), strategic agility refers to the resourceful ability to anticipate, act and respond in a competitively different and relevant ways to the external opportunities and threats thrown up by dynamic business environment through skillful execution of specific strategies tailored to drive value chain activities. It is the ability of a company to respond fast to the changes in the business environment, adapt to the changes and take proactive actions that are aimed at controlling uncertainty. Isaiah and Dickson (2023) viewed strategic agility as the ability to detect, anticipate, sense market opportunities, evolving conditions and other environmental changes and the ability to seize the opportunity with speed and implement new solution. Strategically agile business organizations exhibit characteristic antecedents such as: astute understanding of the market trends (market acuity), business continuity planning, change disposition, organisation learning and IT capability including ability to save millions in project budgets, reducing production cost and application of processes that create value for customers (Bassey *et al.*, 2023). Hutzschenreuter *et al.* (2014) posit that strategic agility are measured in terms of clarity of vision, strategic leadership, core capabilities, strategic sensitivity and strategic resource fluidity (Dheseviano and Ogochukwu, 2023). This study looked at clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core competence.

Clarity of vision provides the organization with the necessary speed for activities and implementation processes and provides motivations for all parties within the value chain that enable them to take advantage of appropriate opportunities. Clarity of vision indicated that vision combines insight and sensing insight indicates a clear picture in the mind, and sensing is the ability to give a mental plan about perceiving events in the future and after providing clarity of vision the organization provides the speed necessary for implementation and enjoying stability. According to Muhammad *et al.* (2020), what is required in investing and exploiting the available opportunities whenever possible is the vision which is a realistic process with more attractive credibility for the future, when organizations face complex

challenges in light of the environment, fluctuating actions provide them with clarity of vision, the speed necessary to take decisions and procedures and implement them with the necessary efficiency and focuses on all companies. According to David, (2013) strategic leadership is anchored on the thinking and visionary capabilities of strategic leadership whose aim is to create an organization that is transformative. Ekanem *et al.* (2023) argue that strategic leadership is not only concerned with the possession of unique abilities that allows for the absorption and learning of new information and ideas, but having the adaptive capacity to appropriately respond to the dynamism and complexity of the external environment.

Core competence often referred to by different names such as distinctive capabilities, organizational competencies or dynamic capabilities. These principal competencies are normally responsible for bringing about success in an organization (Ezeanolue, 2022). These principal competencies provide firms with the enablement through both bad and good economic conditions and are regarded as the most valuable organizational assets for those firms, which possess them, which conversely serve as the frustrating challenges for competing firms that lack these competencies (Isaiah, 2023).

The performance of FMCG firms is influenced by various factors, including market competition, consumer preferences, supply chain efficiency, and technological advancements (Kotler and Keller, 2016). FMCG firms operate in a highly dynamic environment characterized by frequent changes in consumer demand, price sensitivity, and evolving distribution channels. To sustain growth and profitability, firms must continuously adapt to these changes through innovation, effective marketing strategies, and operational efficiency (Aaker, 2021). Therefore, this informed the decision to ascertain the influence of strategic agility on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms' sub-sector of Nigerian economy.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of strategic agility, there exists a significant gap in understanding of its precise impact on the performance of FMCG firms. The fast-moving consumer goods firms in Nigeria operates in a highly dynamic and challenging environment characterized by economic fluctuations, intense competition, regulatory changes, and shifting consumer preferences. To remain competitive and sustain growth, FMCG firms must continuously adapt to these uncertainties. However, many organizations struggle with rigid structures, slow decision-making, lack of clear vision, poor leadership, incompetence's and ineffective resource allocation, which hinder their ability to respond swiftly to market disruptions.

Strategic agility, which encompasses clarity of vision, strategic leadership, core competence, strategic sensitivity and strategic resource fluidity has been identified as a critical factor in enhancing organizational performance. Despite its significance, there is limited empirical evidence on how strategic agility influences the performance of FMCG companies in Nigeria. The lack of strategic agility in many firms has led to inefficiencies, declining market share, poor service quality, reduced profitability and customer satisfaction. This study seeks to examine the impact of strategic agility on the performance of FMCG firms in Nigeria, exploring how clarity of vision, strategic leadership, core capabilities, strategic sensitivity and strategic resource fluidity contribute to competitive advantage, operational efficiency, and overall business sustainability.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to ascertain the influence of strategic agility on the performance of FMCG firms in South West Nigeria. The specific objectives include to;

- i. examine the influence of clarity of vision on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria;
- ii. ascertain the influence of strategic leadership on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria;
- iii. examine the influence of core competence on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria;

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the influence of clarity of vision on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of strategic leadership on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent does core competence affect the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

- Ho₁:** Clarity of vision has no significant influence on the performance of fast moving consumer goods industries in South West Nigeria.
- Ho₂:** Strategic leadership has no significant effect on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria.
- Ho₃:** Core competence has no significant influence on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

The idea and qualitative characteristic of this study were discussed in this section of the study. These include the element that offer comparability, verifiability, timeliness, and ability of strategic agility and the performance of fast-moving consumer goods industries.

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 2.1. Conceptual model of strategic agility and Firms’ Performance by the researcher, 2025.

2.1.1 Concepts of Strategic Agility

The term agility, to which ‘strategic’ derivable from strategy is prefixed, originates from the Latin word *agilitas* which literally means the ability to think and draw inference quickly (intellectual acuity). Agility was first used in the parliamentary proceedings of the House of Lords in Britain presided over by Lord Hinton between 1737 – 1738 in 18th century. The usage of strategic agility by Lord Hinton followed the dismissal of innocent military officers from the army by Her Majesty based on misrepresentation and planned reduction in the strength of the army. The concept of agility was first canvassed in the context of business in 1982 (Walter, 2020). Strategic agility came into the lexicon of contemporary business and strategic management in 20th century around 1990s as a result of a research sponsored by the United State (U.S.), government in 1991 at Iacocca Institute and it has to do with advancement from mass production through lean to present agile manufacturing or production (Nkuda, 2021).

Agility is a broad domain of research of which strategic agility is one of the sub-domains (Haider *et al.*, 2021). The *raison d’être* of agility is in its perception as a solution to cope with the dynamic and ever-evolving business environment (Hamed, 2023). Agility has many types viz: organizational agility, cultural agility, strategic agility, value agility, delivery agility, business agility and learning agility including mental agility. However, Isaiah and Dickson (2023) state that agility incorporates, harnesses, integrates and leverages flexibility, speed, responsiveness and competency to be effective. There are two other concepts to which strategic agility is related notably: flexibility which took root in 1980s and adaptability which is based on contingency approach (Brown *et al.*, 2022). While flexibility relates to operations, strategic agility is market-focused and strategy-oriented (Das, 2001). Strategic agility as a contemporary and emerging concept in strategic management is not so easy to define due to vagueness and variability in some definitions (Sampath and Krishnamoorthy, 2017).

Sarkosi *et al.* (2022), sees strategic agility as the ability of an organization to detect changes through the opportunities and threats existing in the business environment, and to give rapid response through the recombination of resources, processes and strategies. Extensive review of the strategic agility literature shows that an agile organization can be

successful in competitive environment through the abilities of responsiveness, competence, flexibility and speed so that it achieves competitive advantage in the market (Sarkosi *et al.*, 2022). Soltaninezhad *et al.* (2020) considered strategic agility to be a means by which organizations transform, reinvent themselves, adapt, and ultimately survive. They see strategic agility as the capacity of a firm to continuously adjust and adapt its strategic direction in a core business in order to create value for the firm. Sampath and Krishnamoorthy, (2017) considered strategic agility to be about being adaptive to changes in the business context, spotting opportunities, threats and risks, and launching new strategic initiatives rapidly and repeatedly.

2.1.2 Dimensions of Strategic Agility

The dimensions of strategic agility adopted in this study include: clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core capabilities. These dimensions are discussed below:

2.1.2.1 Clarity of Vision

Clarity of vision provides the organization with the necessary speed for activities and implementation processes and provides motivations for all parties within the value chain that enable them to take advantage of appropriate opportunities (Gerald *et al.*, 2020). In the strategic management process, vision forms an integral part of organizational strategic intent and can be described as a statement which articulates and captures what an organization seeks and aspires to become in the future. Other definitions of vision include: it is the process of developing a desirable and attainable goal for the future (Gregorio, 2020). To Hitt *et al.*, (2007, 2013) a vision is a big picture of what the firm wants to be and in broad terms, what it wants to ultimately achieve. The vision provides both the inspiration and motivation upon which the mission statement is crafted to capture the chain of activities an organization should be carrying out in order to achieve the vision ultimately (Saratoga, 2024).

2.1.2.2 Strategic Leadership

Leadership, to which the term ‘strategic’ has been prefixed, is a popular concept in both general management and strategy literature. Recourse to extant literature shows that leadership has been defined in different ways. It is considered as the process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal (Mba *et al.*, 2023). Michael and Lawrence, (2019) viewed leadership as the process of creating a suitable environment and influencing individuals to strive enthusiastically to achieve organizational goals and/or objectives. Leadership can also be regarded as the process whereby an individual creates a vision and not only encourages organizational members to buy in but also rallies and galvanizes their collective efforts to achieve organizational set goals. Similarly, strategy with its root words in Greek “strategos or strategia” meaning art of the general is closely associated with military establishment as reflected in the Chinese general, Sun Tzu’s Art of War as far back as 500BCE (Mueni, and Githira, 2023).

Quantive (2024) describes strategic leadership as being concerned with “transforming an organization through its vision and values, culture and climate and structure and systems as well as strategy. Strategic leadership involves enormous responsibilities on the part of the strategic leaders and organization’s strategists after whose values and world views, organizational culture is often shaped (Reed, 2021). These strategic responsibilities cover the definition of strategic intent, mid-wife of strategy formulation, supervision of strategy implementation and effecting strategy evaluation and control (Salu, 2022).

2.1.2.3 Core Competence

Core competence of an organization can be acquired from factor markets or built up over time from the organizational resources made up of both tangible and intangible via

experience and learning by doing (heuristics) (Harvard Business Review, 2023). The resources represent the repertoire of productive assets owned or possessed by an organization. The deployment of a set of resources to carry out a particular task constitutes what is termed capability (Sampath and Krishnamoorthy, 2017). The term capability and competence can be used interchangeably as any distinction between the terms is merely semantic (Grant, 2008). The resource plus core competencies yield core capability which an organization can deploy to carry out tasks that could lead to gaining competitive advantage (Govuzela, and Mafini, 2019).

2.1.3 Performance

Performance is a fundamental measure of an organization's ability to achieve its strategic objectives effectively and efficiently. It reflects how well a company utilizes its resources to generate value, maintain competitiveness, and sustain long-term growth. In business, performance is often assessed through key indicators such as profitability, market share, customer satisfaction, and operational efficiency. In dynamic and competitive industries such as the FMCG sector, performance is influenced by various internal and external factors, including economic conditions, consumer preferences, technological advancements, and strategic management practices (Muhammad, 2020).

Companies that continuously enhance their performance through innovation, agility, and strategic resource allocation are better positioned to achieve sustainable growth and competitive advantage. Given the rapidly changing business environment, organizations must adopt flexible and adaptive strategies to improve their performance. Understanding the key drivers of performance enables businesses to implement effective strategies that enhance productivity, profitability, and customer satisfaction, ultimately leading to long-term success (Mba *et al.*, 2023).

Performance refers to the measurable aspects of outcome of an organizational process. These aspects are given as reliability, production cycle time and inventory turn. Performance in return affects business performance measures such as market share and customer satisfaction. Imagha *et al.* (2024) noted that performance encompasses indicators such as productivity (cost savings, efficiency) and quality (customer service and percentage of defects). According Bassey *et al.* (2023), through agility, firms would be able to achieve superior performance. Performance improvement in operational terms is particularly interesting when it is able to influence the competitive position of the firm. By being able to deliver superior value and/or offer prices through lower costs a firm will increase customer satisfaction and loyalty and potentially increase its market share and profitability (Kowo and Akinbola, 2019). Operational performance also encompasses the speed of carrying activities in the business. However, consideration of differential execution speeds requires higher order concepts associated with agility (acceleration of variety change) as well as factors that hinder or help agility execution (costs, coordination) (Teece, 2007).

2.1.4 Measures of Firms' Performance

1. Operational Efficiency

Operational efficiency can be defined as the ratio between outputs gained from the business and an input to run a business operation. When improving operation efficiency, the output to input ratio improves. Operation efficiency is often achieved by streamlining a company's core process in order to more effectively respond to continually changing market force in a cost-effective manner (Hillier, 2012). Operational efficiency underpins the

companies' most basic strategic goals. Improving customer satisfaction and increasing shareholder value both depend on achieving operational efficiency. Therefore, improving operational efficiency is one of the companies' top objectives.

Efficiency in operations is an indispensable requirement for organizations to thrive in the intensely competitive business landscape (Habib *et al.*, 2022). Operational efficiency is critical for business organizations as it enables them to offer competitive prices to customers. Research indicates that efficiency is vital in determining a firm's performance. The effective utilization of resources is crucial for enhancing a company's performance; therefore, management should prioritize this aspect (Dalwai and Salehi, 2021).

2. Quality of Service

Quality of service is generally referred to the output of service delivery system, which is linked to consumer satisfaction, perception, and opinions that are formed based on various contributing factors and references. The interest on this issue has grown extensively over the last decade. It has become a very popular field for academic and scholarly research (Zeithmal, 2020). A great amount of models and theories have been developed to address and highlight this matter. Scientific and technological innovations made way for the generation of quality, the more frequency the less gap. In some cases, the best service efforts can be criticized because of the customer's bad mood, according to direct service providers such as waitresses. It is recognized that the practice in influencing customer may be affected by their psychological and physical conditions (Uforo *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the degree of discrepancy between the normative expectations of customers and the perceptions at the state of time may alter.

Service quality is a complex construct that incorporates multiple attributes which may change rapidly and dramatically, which will then facilitate precise measurement (Mason, 2021). Consumers experience and perceive quality during the process whilst providers attain and define them. The total delivery process is then evaluated, especially with those that is constantly repeated, and will gradually maintain long-term customer relations if performed accurately. When designing the process, a key element which is quality will influence the volume of demand for the specific product or customer profile. Quality-based strategy is sustainable and excellent; must be viewed as a strategic force as it can significantly increase market share, drive growth, and pose a barrier to those that seek to replicate.

3. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to the psychological notion that encompasses the feeling of comfort and pleasure that emanates from obtaining what one hopes for and expects (Olaleye *et al.*, 2024). Uzir *et al.* (2021) viewed satisfaction as the feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing the performance (or outcome) of a product or service perceived quality in relation to the buyer's expectation. Bahadır *et al.* (2022) defined Customer satisfaction as a short-term emotional reaction to a specific service performance. Uzir *et al.* (2021) defined Customer satisfaction as the attitude resulting from what customers think should happen (expectations) interacting with what customers think did happen (performance perceptions).

Customer satisfaction in the FMCG sector is a crucial factor influencing brand loyalty, repeat purchases, and overall market competitiveness (Musarapasi and Garanti, 2020). FMCG products, which include everyday essentials such as food, beverages, personal care, and household items, are characterized by high purchase frequency and low consumer involvement in decision-making (Purwanto, 2020). Due to the vast availability of substitutes,

customer satisfaction in this sector depends on product quality, price competitiveness, brand perception, and convenience (Musarapasi and Garanti, 2020).

2.1.5 Strategic agility and Firms' Performance

The fast-moving consumer goods firms in Nigeria operates within a complex and rapidly changing environment, influenced by economic fluctuations, regulatory shifts, and evolving consumer preferences (Uttong et al., 2024). To navigate these challenges and maintain competitiveness, FMCG firms must adopt strategic agility, which encompasses the ability to swiftly sense market changes, make rapid decisions, and efficiently reallocate resources. Strategic Agility and Firm Performance Strategic agility creates organisational ability to continuously, adequately adjust and adapt in appropriate time with the organisation's strategic direction in achieving overall firm performance (Wheelen and Hunger, 2010).

In the 21st century business environment, embracing strategic agility will enhance continuous performance and adequate adjustment of the organisation towards dynamic business environment and adapt in appropriate time (Olaleye *et al.*, 2021). The performance of an organisation depends on its strategic agility measures toward its competitors, customers, suppliers, partners and governments polices. Conceptually, strategic agility is a powerful predictor to guide against negative effect of business environmental changes and for future preparedness in order to outperform other competitors and attaining superior profitability. Studies have emphasized that strategic agility enhance operational productivity, product reliability, quality of service and speed and operational performance (Arokodare, 2020). Most literatures on the link between strategic agility and firm performance in different industries have shown that strategic agility practices by organisations significantly improve firm competitive advantage and overall performance.

2.1.6 Clarity of Vision and Firms' Performance

A well-articulated vision serves as a guiding framework that defines the purpose, aspirations, and strategic direction of the organization. It encapsulates what the firm aims to achieve and how it intends to impact its stakeholders, including employees, customers, and the broader community. A clear vision aligns the efforts of all employees, fostering a sense of shared purpose and commitment. When employees understand the organization's goals and their roles in achieving them, they are more likely to be motivated, engaged, and aligned in their efforts. This alignment not only enhances individual performance but also facilitates collaboration across teams, driving the organization towards its strategic objectives (Saratoga, 2024).

Moreover, a clear vision aids in strategic decision-making. It acts as a compass that guides leaders and employees in making choices that are consistent with the organization's long-term goals. This clarity helps organizations navigate challenges, seize opportunities, and respond effectively to changing market dynamics. Research shows that organizations with a well-defined vision experience higher levels of employee satisfaction and retention, improved performance metrics, and increased competitiveness in their respective markets (Saratoga, 2024; Aithor, 2024). Ultimately, clarity of vision is not merely a statement of intent; it is a critical determinant of an organization's ability to achieve sustainable success and maintain relevance in an ever-evolving business landscape. A clear and compelling vision is fundamental to an organization's success, serving as a guiding beacon that aligns efforts, motivates employees, and drives strategic initiatives.

2.1.7 Strategic Leadership and Firms' Performance

Strategic leadership refers to the ability of leaders to influence an organization's direction and performance through effective strategy formulation and execution. It encompasses various competencies, including vision creation, resource allocation, decision-making, and the ability to inspire and motivate employees (Quantive, 2024). Strategic leadership is a critical component in determining an organization's overall success and sustainability in today's dynamic business environment. It encompasses the abilities and actions of leaders to influence and guide their organizations toward achieving long-term objectives while navigating challenges and leveraging opportunities. Effective strategic leaders possess a clear vision, make informed decisions, allocate resources efficiently, and inspire their teams, all of which are essential for driving organizational performance.

The role of strategic leadership in shaping a firm's success can be observed in several key areas. First, a well-defined vision set by strategic leaders provides direction and purpose for the organization. When employees understand the long-term goals and strategic objectives, they are more likely to align their efforts toward achieving those goals, resulting in improved cohesion and effectiveness. Second, strategic leaders are instrumental in fostering a positive organizational culture that emphasizes innovation, collaboration, and accountability (Mba *et al.*, 2023). By promoting an environment that encourages employee engagement and empowerment, leaders can enhance workforce motivation, leading to increased productivity and reduced turnover rates. Research indicates that organizations with strong strategic leadership experience higher levels of employee satisfaction, which directly contributes to firm success.

2.1.8 Core Competence and Firms' Performance

Core competence, often referred to as core capabilities, are the unique strengths and resources that enable an organization to deliver value and gain a competitive advantage in its industry. These capabilities encompass a combination of specialized skills, knowledge, technologies, and processes that are not easily replicated by competitors. The significance of core capabilities in determining a firm's success is widely recognized, as they directly influence various aspects of organizational performance, innovation, and strategic positioning. Organizations that effectively identify, develop, and leverage their core capabilities are better positioned to differentiate themselves in the marketplace. Prahalad and Hamed (2023) emphasized that firms that cultivate their core competencies can exploit market opportunities more effectively and respond to competitive pressures with agility. This ability to adapt and innovate is particularly crucial in today's rapidly changing business environment, where consumer preferences and technological advancements are constantly evolving.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Dynamic Capability Perspective (DCP)

Dynamic capability perspective or theory is keenly associated with the work of David Teece and his associates in the late 1990s (Teece, 2007). Grant (2008) relying on these dynamic capability pioneers, define dynamic capability as the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments. On this score, dynamic capabilities become relevant and relate to strategic agility which business organizations require, given their experience of constantly changing

operating environment, to help them pursue competitive advantage. Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) is the capability of an organization to purposefully adapt an organization's resource base. DCT, which was developed by Teece et al. (1997) was defined as the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing environments" and it examines how firms address or bring about changes in their turbulent business environment through reconfiguration of their firm-specific competencies into new competencies (Teece, 2007). The concept of DCT explained the mechanism that links resources and product markets to competitive advantage and firm survival. The DCT further explain how firms gain sustainable competitive advantage, survive in competitive and turbulence business environment in several ways.

2.3 Empirical Review

Previous studies have been carried out in this direction. In this section of the study, few of such studies were considered are shown hereunder:

Alkandi and Helmi (2024) studied the impact of strategic agility on organizational performance: the mediating role of market orientation and innovation capabilities in emerging industrial sector. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of SA on OP, among others. Cross-sectional research design was adopted for the study. A total of 300 Managers working in various companies listed in Saudi Arabia represented the research population and sample size of the study. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to test the proposed model, following a two-stage approach that entails a measurement model and a causal structural model. A positive relationship was found among the variables. It was recommended that by implementing a differentiation strategy, for example, an organization can establish its strategic position and eventually increase its profitability. This study was similar to the present study in terms of variables used in this study and is different to the present study in both content and geographical scope.

Mutunga *et al.* (2024) assessed Influence of Strategic Leadership on the Performance of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Nairobi County. The objective of the study was to determine the influence of strategic leadership on the performance of pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Nairobi County. Descriptive research design was used in the study. A total of 71 pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Nairobi County served as the population of the study, while 288 respondents were used as sample size, as determined using a Taro Yamane formula. Data that was analyzed using descriptive and inferential analysis were done. Findings revealed a positive relationship among the variables. It was concluded that strategic leadership had a positive and significant influence on the performance of pharmaceutical companies in Nairobi County. The researchers recommended that the top pharmaceutical companies in Nairobi county invest in leadership development programs to enhance the capabilities of their leaders which can be tailored to communication training, vision-casting, or even inspirational leadership programs to help in offering better leadership which enhances organizational performance. This study is similar to the present study in terms of objective of the study and has different view in the area of study and methodology.

Imagha *et al.*, (2024) assessing the influence of strategic agility on the performance of selected manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to assess the influence of strategic agility on selected manufacturing firms' performance in South-south Nigeria. Population for the study was 319 staff of selected quoted manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria. 177 was arrived at as sample size, using Taro Yamene's formula for sample size determination. Primary and secondary sources of data were adopted for the study.

Proportionate sampling technique was used to guarantee efficient representation of the selected firm while the research instrument was a structure questionnaire. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used in analyzing the study. Findings showed that core competencies revealed a high correlation value of $R = 0.882$ with an Unstandardized Coefficient Beta $\beta=0.766$. While strategic sensitivity revealed an Unstandardized Coefficient Beta of $\beta=0.530$. From the findings, it was concluded that strategic agility has a positive significant influence on selected manufacturing firms' performance in South-south Nigeria. As recommendations, the studied manufacturing firms should imbibe core competency as a policy if they are to attain competitive advantage, being that core competencies are the foundation upon which a company builds its business and drives its success. Also, management of the selected studied manufacturing firms should develop strategic sensitivity as this will actively help in scanning the environment, and engaging in scenario planning exercises. Both studies are similar in terms of subject matter and variables used both has different view in the area of study and geographical context.

Ekanem *et al.* (2023) examined strategic sensitivity and firm competitiveness in selected deposit money banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The objective of the study was to examine the relationship between strategic sensitivity and firm competitiveness of deposit money banks in Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design approach was adopted for the study. The target respondents were staffs of 11 Deposit Money Banks operating within the study area, while the sample size was 180 employees of the banks as determined using systematic sampling technique. Data gathered were analyzed with the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis. It is concluded that there is a significant relationship between strategic sensitivity and firms' competitiveness. It is recommended, among others that, the deposit money banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State need to build strong capabilities. This study was similar to the present study in terms of objective of the study and has different view in the area of study and methodology.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The survey research design was employed in this study by the researcher to create a better understanding of individual or group viewpoints concerning a specific concept or issue of interest. Since the focus of this study is on the experiences of people working in Nigeria's fast-moving consumer goods sector, both qualitative and quantitative methods was used to investigate the topic's holistic character.

3.2 Population of the study

There are forty-three (43) firms in Nigeria's fast-moving consumer goods industry but six (6) were specifically chosen for the research. The chosen companies were the first generation and leading companies in Nigeria's fast-moving consumer goods sectors and have participated in several contests and new product development.

3.3 Sampling Techniques and sampling Size Determination

The sampling distribution approach was considered a critical topic in research to prevent bias in data collection. stratified sampling techniques was used in this study to choose its respondents, guaranteeing that each member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen. Accuracy cannot be guaranteed by a large sample size. Therefore, the researcher specified the sample size within the target population.

For calculating sample sizes, this study used Krejcie and Morgan Formula, which is stated as follows: $s = \frac{x^2 np(1-p)}{[d^2(n-1) + x^2 p(1-p)]}$ model 3.1

Where:

n = require sample size

X² = the table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.841), same as (1.96). (1.96)

N = the population size

P = the population proportion (assumed to be .50 since this would provide the maximum sample size)

d = the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (.50)

Since **N = 1,002**

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{3.841(1002)(0.5)(1-0.5)}{[0.05^2(1002-1) + 3.841(0.5)(1-0.5)]} \\ &= \frac{3.841(1002)(0.5)(0.5)}{[0.0025(1001) + 3.841(0.5)(0.5)]} \\ &= \frac{962.1705}{(2.5025 + 0.96025)} \\ &= \frac{962.1705}{3.46275} \\ &= 277 \end{aligned}$$

Sample size (n) = 277.

In distributing questionnaire, issues such as non-response, attribution or outliers are common which may result in a significant reduction in the total number of effectively filled and returned copies of the questionnaire. Top account for such shortfall, it is recommended in the literature to increase the copies of questionnaire for distribution between 10-20 per cent (Edwards *et al.*, 2002). This indicates that the number of questionnaire disseminated was greater than the number necessary to achieve the specified level of precision or confidence interval width. Therefore, it is anticipated that the least 75% of the copies of the questionnaire given were returned and deemed useful. It is a good statistical practice to increase distribution above the sample size. Thus, the distributed copies were increase by 20 per cent. As a result, the distribution adjustment is

$$n = 277 + (0.2)(277) = 277 + 55.4 = 332$$

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as frequencies and percentages. Also, inferential statistical tool such as multiple regressions was used for testing the hypotheses. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) would be used as the statistical software package.

4. Presentation of Data Analysis of Empirical Data

4.1 Examine the influence of clarity of vision on the performance of FMCG firms in South West Nigeria

Table 4.1 Responses on the influence of Clarity of Vision on the Performance of FMCG Firms

S/N	Clarity of Vision Dimension	SA	A	N	D	SD
Q1	Our organization's vision is clearly communicated to all employees.	67 (25.0)	90 (33.6)	13 (4.9)	78 (29.1)	20 (7.5)
Q2	The vision of the organization aligns with its current strategic priorities.	66 (24.6)	79 (29.5)	20 (7.5)	31 (11.6)	72 (26.9)
Q3	Our vision is realistic and achievable within the specified timeline.	71 (26.5)	81 (30.2)	16 (6.0)	57 (21.3)	42 (16.0)
Q4	The vision motivates us to strive for excellence in our work.	85 (31.7)	78 (29.1)	10 (3.7)	31 (11.6)	64 (23.9)
Q5	Our organization's vision resonates with employees and creates a sense of purpose	97 (36.2)	77 (28.7)	21 (7.8)	28 (10.4)	45 (16.8)

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The analysis in Table 4.1 shows that a total of 67 respondents representing 25.0% strongly agreed that our organization's vision is clearly communicated to all employees. A total of 90 respondents representing 33.6% ticked agree, 13 (4.9%) ticked undecided, 78 (29.1%) respondents ticked disagree and 20 (7.5%) respondents ticked strongly agreed.

With regards to the second question, a total of 66 respondents representing 24.6% strongly agreed that the vision of the organization aligns with its current strategic priorities. A total of 79 respondents representing 29.5% ticked agree, 20 (7.5%) ticked undecided, 31 (11.6%) respondents ticked disagree and 72 (26.9%) respondents ticked strongly agreed.

With regards to third question, 71 respondents representing 26.5% strongly agreed that our vision is realistic and achievable within the specified timeline. A total of 81 respondents representing 30.2% ticked agree, 16 (6.0%) ticked strongly disagree, 57 (21.3%) respondents ticked disagree and 42 (16.0%) respondent ticked undecided.

With regards to fourth question shows that a total of 85 respondents representing 31.7% strongly agreed that the vision motivates us to strive for excellence in our work. A total of 78 respondents representing 29.1% ticked agree, 10 (3.7%) ticked strongly disagree, 31 (11.6%) respondents ticked disagree and 64 (23.9%) respondent ticked undecided.

With regards to fifth question, a total of 97 respondents representing 36.2% strongly agreed that our organization's vision resonates with employees and creates a sense of purpose. A total of 77 respondents representing 28.7% ticked agree, 21 (7.8%) ticked strongly disagree, 28 (10.4%) respondents ticked disagree and 45 (16.8%) respondent ticked undecided.

4.2 Ascertain the influence of strategic leadership on the performance of FMCG firms in South West Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Responses on the influence of strategic leadership on the performance of FMCG

S/N	Strategic Leadership Dimension	SA	A	N	D	SD
Q6	Leaders in this organization provide a clear and compelling vision for the future.	96 (35.8)	64 (23.9)	22 (8.9)	76 (28.4)	10 (3.7)
Q7	Leadership effectively communicates long-term strategic priorities to employees.	70 (26.1)	101 (37.1)	45 (16.8)	28 (10.4)	24 (9.0)
Q8	Our organization's strategic leaders makes informed and timely decisions based on accurate data and analysis.	107 (39.9)	51 (19.0)	74 (27.6)	23 (8.6)	13 (4.9)
Q9	Our organization's leaders demonstrate flexibility in adjusting strategies to align with changing circumstances.	74 (27.6)	84 (31.3)	72 (26.9)	27 (10.1)	11 (4.1)
Q10	Our firm's strategic leaders encourage innovation and creative thinking to achieve strategic goals	49 (18.3)	91 (34.0)	76 (28.4)	30 (11.2)	22 (8.2)

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The analysis in Table 4.2 shows that a total of 96 respondents representing 35.8% strongly agreed that leaders in this organization provide a clear and compelling vision for the future. A total of 64 respondents representing 23.9% ticked agree, 22 (8.9%) ticked undecided, 76 (28.4%) respondents ticked disagree and 10 (3.7%) respondents ticked strongly agreed.

With regards to the second question, a total of 70 respondents representing 26.1% strongly agreed that leadership effectively communicates long-term strategic priorities to employees. A total of 101 respondents representing 37.1% ticked agree, 45 (16.8%) ticked undecided, 28 (10.4%) respondents ticked disagree and 24 (9.0%) respondents ticked strongly agreed.

With regards to third question, 107 respondents representing 39.9% strongly agreed that our organization's strategic leaders make informed and timely decisions based on accurate data and analysis. A total of 51 respondents representing 19.0% ticked agree, 74 (27.6%) ticked strongly disagree, 23 (8.6%) respondents ticked disagree and 13 (4.9%) respondent ticked undecided.

With regards to fourth question shows that a total of 74 respondents representing 27.6% strongly agreed that our organization's leaders demonstrate flexibility in adjusting strategies to align with changing circumstances. A total of 84 respondents representing 31.3% ticked agree, 72 (26.9%) ticked strongly disagree, 27 (10.1%) respondents ticked disagree and 11 (4.1%) respondent ticked undecided.

With regards to fifth question, a total of 47 respondents representing 18.3% strongly agreed that our firm's strategic leaders encourage innovation and creative thinking to achieve strategic goals. A total of 91 respondents representing 34.0% ticked agree, 76 (28.4%) ticked strongly disagree, 30 (11.2%) respondents ticked disagree and 22 (8.2%) respondent ticked undecided.

4.3 Examine the influence of core capabilities on the performance of FMCG firms in South West Nigeria

Table 4.3 Responses on the influence of core capabilities on the performance FMCG

S/N	Core Competence Dimension	SA	A	N	D	SD
Q11	Our firm has a pool of talented people with specialised skills.	91 (34.0)	92 (34.3)	21 (7.8)	40 (14.9)	24 (9.0)
Q12	we possess the expertise required to maintain a competitive advantage.	74 (27.6)	67 (25.0)	59 (22.0)	38 (14.2)	30 (11.2)
Q13	Our organization leverages its core competencies to enter new markets.	86 (32.1)	61 (22.8)	25 (9.3)	64 (23.9)	32 (11.9)
Q14	Our organization's has a clear focus on fostering a culture of innovation within the organization.	78 (27.6)	84 (31.3)	19 (7.1)	51 (19.1)	24 (9.0)
Q15	Our organization's operational systems and workflows are well-coordinated and adaptable to change.	86 (32.1)	80 (29.9)	17 (6.3)	17 (6.3)	68 (25.4)

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2025)

The analysis in Table 4.3 shows that a total of 91 respondents representing 34.0% strongly agreed that our firm has a pool of talented people with specialised skills, knowledge and technical competencies which make up our corporate strengths to pursue competitive advantage over our rival firms. A total of 92 respondents representing 34.3% ticked agree, 21 (7.8%) ticked undecided, 40 (14.9%) respondents ticked disagree and 24 (9.0%) respondents ticked strongly agreed.

With regards to the second question, a total of 74 respondents representing 27.6% strongly agreed that our organization's employees possess the expertise required to maintain a competitive advantage. A total of 67 respondents representing 25.0% ticked agree, 59 (22.0%) ticked undecided, 38 (14.2%) respondents ticked disagree and 30 (11.2%) respondents ticked strongly agreed.

With regards to third question, 86 respondents representing 32.1% strongly agreed that our organization leverages its core competencies to enter new markets. A total of 61 respondents representing 22.8% ticked agree, 25 (9.3%) ticked strongly disagree, 64 (23.9%) respondents ticked disagree and 32 (11.9%) respondent ticked undecided.

With regards to fourth question shows that a total of 78 respondents representing 27.6% strongly agreed that our organization's has a clear focus on fostering a culture of innovation within the organization. A total of 84 respondents representing 31.3% ticked agree, 19 (7.1%) ticked strongly disagree, 51 (19.1%) respondents ticked disagree and 24 (9.0%) respondent ticked undecided.

With regards to fifth question, a total of 86 respondents representing 32.1% strongly agreed that our organization's operational systems and workflows are well-coordinated and adaptable to change. A total of 80 respondents representing 29.9% ticked agree, 17 (6.3%) ticked strongly disagree, 17 (6.3%) respondents ticked disagree and 68 (25.4%) respondent ticked undecided.

Hypotheses Testing

In the construct of conceptual model, three null hypotheses were used for the study. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regressions. These hypotheses result are presented.

Table 4.4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.774 ^a	.599	.591	.46525

a. Predictors: (Constant), Clarity_Vision, Strategic_Leadership, Core_Capabilities

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	84.547	5	16.909	78.119	.000 ^b
	Residual	56.711	262	.216		
	Total	141.258	267			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Clarity_Vision, Strategic_Leadership, Core_Capabilities

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
1	(Constant)	.492	.154		3.191	.002
	Strategic_Sensitivity	.151	.063	.171	2.387	.018
	Strategic_Resou_Fluidity	.574	.073	.557	7.830	.000
	Clarity_Vision	.196	.072	.218	2.719	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Researchers Computation (2025)

A multiple linear regression analysis was carried out to examine the influence of clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core competencies. on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria. The multiple regression analysis produced an R square of 0.599 as a result. This indicates that 59.9 per cent of change in strategic agility variables can account for 59.9 percent of change in the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria. The model demonstrates a strong goodness of fit with F-statistic of 78.119 and a significant value of 0.000(p-value < 0.001). This suggests that utilising the responses, the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in South West, Nigeria has a statistically significant influence with all strategic agility related parameters taken together. Because the there is a statistically significant relationship

between strategic agility variables and the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms, the null hypothesis that there is no significant combined influence of clarity of vision, strategic leadership, and core capabilities, on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria is rejected. Rather, the alternate hypothesis that there is significant combined influence of clarity of vision, strategic leadership, core capabilities on the performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria is accepted.

4.5 Discussion of the Findings

The study was carried out to ascertain the influence of strategic agility on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms (FMCG) in South West Nigeria. The result of the study showed that there is a significant influence of strategic agility dimensions of (clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core capabilities on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria. These findings are in agreement with several studies in the literature (Tanui, 2023; Ekanem *et al.*, 2023; Imagha *et al.*, 2024; Mutunga *et al.*, 2024; Alkandi and Helmi, 2024). Among, the variables of strategic agility in a joint regression model, strategic resource fluidity showed a high t-test score of 7.830. t-test shows the strength of the causal effect of the variable on the dependent variables.

5. Conclusion

From the study conducted, it is obvious that clarity of vision, strategic leadership, core capabilities. Strategic sensitivity and strategic resource fluidity are relational dimensions that can influence the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms. The empirical results of the study clearly underscore the following:

- i. Clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core capabilities are significant positive determinants of the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria
- ii. Firms that consider the application of strategic agility dimensions such as Clarity of vision, strategic leadership and core capabilities are likely to record a better Key Performance Indicator (KPI).
- iii. Although all three strategic agility dimensions used in this study were statistically significant, the coefficient for core competence was seen as the dimension that had the highest significant influence at 0.683 on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in South West Nigeria.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Firms in the FMCG should see clarity of vision as a strategic asset that drives consistency, innovation, and market leadership. By aligning their vision with consumer expectations, fostering agility, and reinforcing communication, FMCG firms can maintain relevance and achieve sustainable growth in dynamic markets.
- ii. Firms in the FMCG should see strategic leadership as fundamental to the sustained success of FMCG companies. By embracing innovation, agility, brand positioning, cost efficiency, talent development, and digital transformation, leaders can navigate industry challenges and drive long-term growth. FMCG firms should invest in strong, visionary leadership to remain competitive in an evolving market landscape.

- iii. Firms in the FMCG should identify and refine unique strengths that set them apart from competitors to remain relevant in a dynamic market, FMCG firms must continuously enhance their core strengths while adapting to emerging trends and consumer needs.

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